

Breath and Lungs health Analyzer with Respiratory Analyzer over Internet of Things (IoT) Protocol IPV6

¹MATTAM ROHITH, ²KOTREDDY DHARMENDRA REDDY, ³JAGGAVARAPU NAVEEN,
⁴PILLALAMARRI LAXMAN

Rohithtron26@gmail.com, dharmendramec222@gmail.com ,
Student @ St.Martin's Engg College-Hyderabad
Pillalamarri Laxman
Asst.Professor in St.Martin's Engg College-Hyderabad
Research Scholar of Lovely Professional University – Panjab.
Email:laxmanabcd@gmail.com

Abstract

Now a day's portable / compact biomedical devices are becoming daily needs of people with chronic diseases. The proposed method is a compact low power device model for measuring human body vital signals through which lungs health can be monitored onboard and by internet form anywhere on earth with existing IoT technology. Tele medicine has already become popular where patient vitals can be scanned by a remote doctor and appropriate medicine prescription can be given; such type of situation the proposed system is more useful.

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*Corresponding Author

E-mail Address:rohithtron26@gmail.com

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